

Refsum Disease

Description:

Causes

Refsum disease is a recessive genetic mutation caused by a deficiency in phytanoyl-coenzyme A hydroxylase as well as the PHYH gene being deficient. The genetic mutation in the PHYH and PEX7 genes results in the accumulation of phytanic acid in the body.

Pathology & Diagnosis

The diagnosis of Refsum disease is based on many clinical examinations including ophthalmology, olfactory, and neurology. Ophthalmology is performed to assess retinitis pigmentosa in which nyctalopia can be found. An early symptom of the disease is the progressive damage of the rod cells, leading to a constricted visual field and impaired visual acuity, which results from damage to cone cells as the disease progresses. Ophthalmology is tested via visual field testing, optical coherence imaging, contrast acuity, and electroretinography. Olfactory testing, specifically anosmia testing, is performed to assess the patient's sense of smell. The buildup of phytanic acid in the body damages the nervous system, including the olfactory nerves, leading to loss of vision, smell, hearing, and balance. Anosmia is tested with an odor identification test or a scratch and sniff test, like the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT). Any neurology testing is to test for Peripheral polyneuropathy—damage to nerves in the peripheral nervous system. Symptoms such as cerebellar ataxia, skeletal dysplasia, and Ichthyosis are used to diagnose refsum disease.

Cerebellar ataxia is the inability of the brain to regulate body posture and movements, which is a direct result of a defective cerebellum. Skeletal dysplasia refers to bone abnormalities of the tubular bones in the hands or feet as well as abnormal growth plates at the knees, elbows, and shoulders. Finally, ichthyosis is a distinct type of scaliness in the skin, with the scale of the scaliness ranging across the body.

Prognosis & Physiology

The course of refsum disease can vary significantly depending on the treatment prescribed, the progression of the disease, and age of the individual. Currently, there are 2 treatments for refsum disease: a low phytanic acid diet—a long term treatment aimed at restricting phytanic acid intake—and the direct removal of phytanic acid through a dialysis-type process, which is more of an immediate treatment for hospitalized patients. The prognosis of refsum relies heavily on the adherence to a strict phytanic acid diet, which also helps minimize symptoms and slow the loss of the senses. Early diagnosis also plays a role in the prognosis of refsum, it is vital in preventing irreversible nerve damage, which can halt or slow the progression of neurological symptoms. There are two versions of refsum disease: infantile and adult. Children with infantile refsum disease typically experience severe developmental disabilities and a shorter lifespan. Adult refsum is more manageable, as adults can reduce their phytanic acid intake to minimize symptoms. Refsum disease is a rare genetic disorder, which does not fall under the branch of biology.

Traditional Treatments

Traditional treatments of Refsum disease are dietary management, plasmapheresis, and supportive treatment. Dietary management mainly focuses on limiting the intake of high-phytanic acid foods, such as meats, dairy products, and fish. It is also important for those with Refsum to avoid fasting or rapid weight loss, which release phytanic acid stored in fat and liver tissues into the bloodstream. Plasmapheresis is a blood-filtering procedure to rapidly remove high levels of phytanic acid from the blood and is an acute treatment. Supportive treatments are to negate the symptoms experienced by Refsum patients. For example, hydrating creams and other dermatologic drugs are recommended for dry, scaly skin. Cochlear implants can be used to restore hearing in severe patient cases.

Background Information

Refsum disease was established in 1945 by Norwegian neurologist Sigvald Refsum. It was originally called heredoataxia hemeralopica polyneuritiformis but was changed to heredopathia atactica polyneuritiformis the following year. In 1963, Klenk and Kahlke discovered that patients with Refsum disease accumulate phytanic acid, a branched-chain fatty acid, in their tissues and body fluids. In **1967**, Steinberg and colleagues showed that the disease is caused by a defect in the initial α -oxidation step of phytanic acid breakdown. They also demonstrate that phytanic acid is derived exclusively from the diet, and that a diet low in phytanic acid can lead to clinical improvement. In **1997**, Jansen and colleagues identified the specific enzyme that is deficient in Refsum disease: phytanoyl-CoA hydroxylase.

How does it Affect Neurophysiology?

Refsum disease affects neurophysiology through the buildup of phytanic acid in the body which affects the myelin sheath surrounding nerve cells. This leads to a progressive neurodegenerative condition characterized by peripheral neuropathy (motor and sensory nerve damage), cerebellar ataxia (coordination problems), and damage to cranial nerves. These neurological impairments manifest as muscle weakness, numbness, loss of deep reflexes, and difficulty with balance.

Treatment Patient Criteria

The main patient criteria for traditional treatments are a confirmed diagnosis and high blood phytanic levels. The treatments of refsum disease are targeted towards lowering phytanic levels in an individual's bloodstream, hence why a confirmed diagnosis and having high blood phytanic levels is a requirement. Due to treatments of refsum disease having specific treatments for both long-term and acute treatment, that adds on an additional requirement for a patient: if they are experiencing severe symptoms of refsum disease, an acute treatment is necessary.

Treatment Advantages and Disadvantages

Some advantages of dietary management as a refsum treatment are that it can resolve or even improve symptoms, provide potential for visual recovery, and improve long-term prognosis. Through limiting your phytanic acid intake, not only will one be able to reduce the overload of phytanic acid in their body, they will also slow down the progression of the disease, allowing them to live longer and potentially reverse the damage to their nerve cells. The disadvantages of dietary management are that it is a life-long commitment, there are dietary

challenges, and the diet is difficult to manage. Dietary management is a very strict diet that restricts high phytanic level foods. But such foods, such as meat, fish, and dairy products, are a staple to everyday life and trying to avoid them will impact an individual's lifestyle. There are many restrictions and challenges to dietary management, such as the prohibition of fasting or sudden weight loss. Not only might this clash with someone's religion, it requires careful management and can be hard to uphold, especially during illness or surgery. Lastly, the diet required can be hard to manage as there are many foods and even medications that can interfere with phytanic acid metabolism. There is no unavailable treatment, but there are limitations of treatment, especially for reversing existing damage.

Experimental Treatments

The Global DARE Foundation has funded research to test 100 foods for their phytanic acid content and update previous measurements, which can help patients manage their diet more effectively.

Background Information

The Global DARE Foundation is funding research to test foods that are safe for refsum patients to eat. This is significant as their diet is severely limited by the high amounts of phytanic acid in every food, and is further emphasized through that fact that prior to the Global DARE Foundation, only 150 foods had been tested as safe for refsum patients.

Settings of Conduction

The Global DARE Foundation was founded in 2019 and has supported research in various settings around the world. It continues to be active to this day, funding studies and extensive testings to expand the diet for those with refsum disease. It is also hosting educational seminars to spread awareness for refsum disease and further boost its funding and support for further research.

Participant Selection Criteria

The Global DARE Foundation has many different programs which have different requirements for participants. For a research-based program such as their program with Novartis, an internship focused on clinical trials, such requirements were being an MSc, PhD, or MD student from a low- and middle-income country in fields like natural or pharmaceutical sciences, with a preferred research background in specific diseases and strong English communication skills. Different programs, such as the Danish-American Research Exchange program, have different participant criteria, providing different opportunities and support for participants.

Phasing

The Global DARE Foundation is in its growth and expansion phase, having recently celebrated its 5th year anniversary. It is currently focused on continued expansion, such as the recent introduction of new food testing for the dietary guidelines, and the launch of an international Country Ambassador Program to raise awareness across continents.

Citations:

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